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STUDY OF ON-SITE UPGRADED LIVESTOCK BIOGAS PRODUCTION AND CARBON EMISSION REDUCTION BY SUBSTITUTING COALS FOR THERMAL POWER GENERATION

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this project is to integrate a farm-scale bio-desulfurization facility with a novel biogas hollow fibre adsorption module for biogas desulfurization and bio-natural gas production. In this study, the desulfurization experimental results showed that the bio-desulfurization system can remove $96.7 \pm 6\%$ of H_2S from the biogas after an approximately two-month enrichment period. The average CH_4 , N_2 , and CO_2 concentrations in raw biogas were 63.4, 15.2, and 21.1%, respectively. As for biogas upgrading experiments, the inlet biogas flow rates were applied from 5 to 20 L/min. The removal efficiency of CO_2 under all biogas flow rates was 100%. Meanwhile, methane was promoted from 60% to nearly 94% (i.e. 57% increase in methane concentration). The replacement of anthracite and coking coal by upgraded biogas might reduce 44.4% and 42.5% of CO_2 equivalent, respectively. The achievement of this project pursues the mitigation of carbon dioxide emissions by using upgraded pig biogas which can be enlarged and extended to all decentralized pig farms worldwide.

KEYWORDS: Livestock biogas, Bio-desulfurization, Biogas upgrading, Bio-natural gas.

1. INTRODUCTION

World meat production reached 337 million tonnes in 2020, up 45 percent, or 104 million tonnes compared with 2000 (FAO, 2022). Pig meat represented 33 percent of the total in 2020, compared to 39 percent in 2000 (FAO, 2022). African swine fever started affecting Asian countries in late 2018 and continued in 2019 and 2020. It resulted in an 11 million tonnes decrease in world pig meat production between 2018 and 2019 but kept constraining production in 2020 (FAO, 2022). Pig slurry or piggery wastewater can be anaerobically treated to produce biogas as a potential sustainable cleaner energy.

Pig farming is the dominant livestock industry in terms of production value totaling around US\$5.6 billion, i.e., about 33% of agricultural production value (US\$16.8 billion) in 2021 (COA, 2021). Moreover, pig farming production value (USD 2.4 billion) is about 43% of livestock production value (USD 5.6 billion) in 2020 (COA, 2021). In 2022, Taiwan had 6,133 pig farms with a total of 5,375,109 pigs (COA, 2022). However, Taiwan had only 1,540 pig farms (25% of the total farms) with more than 1000 pigs each. These farms constitute 71.5% (3,844,139 pigs) of the total number of pigs. The organic waste produced from livestock farms including animal manure, sludge, wastewater, and other organic wastes can be recycled as a renewable energy source by anaerobic digestion (AD) to avoid polluting the environment (Su, 2020). The collection of biogas from pig farms is used for power generation or direct combustion (Su and Chen, 2015). Anaerobic co-digestion of animal manure and crops provides a combined production of renewable energy and organic fertilizer on organic farms and has been suggested as an option to improve the operation model of organic agriculture. The analytical results of anaerobic digestion and biogas production on a 1000-ha model farm with combined dairy and cash crop production in Denmark were presented (Pugesgaard *et al.*, 2013). The effects on crop rotation as well as greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions were assessed for four scenarios of biogas production with animal manure. The authors concluded that the production of biogas on the experimental farms holds the possibility for the farms to accomplish a positive energy balance providing self-support with organic fertilizer nitrogen and decreasing GHG emissions.

In Taiwan, however, biogas is mainly produced from livestock farms livestock biogas with livestock wastewater, i.e. animal manure mixed with cleaning water, after solid/liquid separation. Thus, the amount of biogas was less than that without solid/liquid separation and the contents of biogas from piggery wastewater were about 60 – 70 % CH₄, 30 % CO₂, and a little H₂S (Su *et al.*, 2003; Su and Chen, 2018). The H₂S in biogas can corrode engines and gas pipelines (McCarthy, 1998). On the other hand, the high content of CO₂ in biogas reduces its heating value and restricts its applications (Abatzoglou and Boivin, 2009). These gases, CO₂ as well as H₂S, can decrease biogas combustion efficiency and cause corrosion problems, respectively.

For biogas desulfurization purposes, a novel farm-scale biogas bio-desulfurization system (BBS) was developed and applied for on-site livestock biogas desulfurization by the research team of Animal Technology Institute Taiwan (ATIT) (Su *et al.*, 2008) and National Taiwan University (NTU) (Su *et al.*, 2013, 2014). Additionally, a biogas photocatalytic desulfurization reactor (PDR) was also successfully developed for small-scale biogas desulfurization purposes (Su and Hong, 2020) as well as in coordination with pilot-scale hollow fibre adsorption module (HFAM) for CO₂ removal by the research team of NTU (Su and Chung, 2021).

For biogas upgrading purposes, there are some applications for upgrading desulfurized biogas, including pressurized water scrubbing, amine swing absorption, pressure swing adsorption, temperature swing adsorption, cryogenic separation, and membrane technologies. The main operations available on the market are absorption, adsorption, cryogenic separation, and membrane separation (Chen *et al.*, 2015). Absorption can be classified into physical and chemical methods. High-pressure water scrubbing and organic physical scrubbing are physical absorptions (Cozm *et al.*, 2013). Physical absorptions have advantages such as simplicity, high methane purity, less methane loss, and low operating and maintenance costs (0.26 USD/m³ biogas). However, they require large amounts of water, high energy demand, chances of biological contamination, and external heat (Adnan *et al.*, 2019). Chemical absorptions, such as amine scrubbing and inorganic solvent scrubbing, can dissolve more CO₂ per unit volume and have a faster processor, but they require high energy to produce steam (0.44 USD/m³ biogas), pre-treatment, and difficulties in handling solvents (Adnan *et al.*, 2019). Adsorption operations can be characterized as pressure swing adsorption, vacuum swing adsorption, temperature swing adsorption, and electrical swing adsorption. Adsorption operations have advantages such as high gas quality, low methane losses, dry process, low energy demand (0.26 USD/m³ biogas), and no chemical use. However, they are complex, require pre-treatment, and need multiple streams to increase biogas quality (Adnan *et al.*, 2019). Cryogenic operation is a distillation process operated under very low temperatures (close to -170 °C) and high pressure (around 80 bar). This process allows introducing of high flow rates of raw biogas and reaching high CH₄ concentrations in the range of 90–99 %. Cryogenic separation produces high-quality biogas and

liquid bio-methane with low additional energy but has high investment and operational costs, requires pre-treatment and high energy for cooling, and is still under development (Adnan *et al.*, 2019). For membrane technology, it is based on gas diffusion and dissolution into polymer materials. Membrane separation has low energy consumption, low cost, and a simple process but has low membrane selectivity, requires pre-treatment, and results in low methane purity. (Adnan *et al.*, 2019; Chen *et al.*, 2015). To promote CH₄ concentration in the desulfurized biogas, a hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption system was introduced and applied for biogas upgrading. (Vogler *et al.*, 2013; Falbo *et al.*, 2014; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2018; Žák *et al.*, 2018 Tantikhajorngosol *et al.*, 2019; Su and Chung, 2021).

A feed-in tariff (FIT) is a policy tool designed to promote investment in renewable energy sources such as photovoltaics, wind, waste, biomass, geothermal, marine, or hydro. Sustainable investing directs investment capital to companies that seek to fight climate change and environmental devastation while promoting corporate responsibility. A FIT can be applied to international market applications including the energy market, energy infrastructure, and technological conditions of each country. However, FITs usually expire after a limited period, because of the irregular electricity supply of renewable electricity sources (RESs), market alterations, and insufficient flexibility options, limited participation in wholesale electricity markets is a viable business model for RES no longer receiving FITs (Rövekamp *et al.*, 2021).

The objective was to study the feasibility of combining a farm-scale bio-desulphurization facility with a hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption module (HFAM) for biogas upgrading. The acceptable H₂S in the biogas for livestock biogas applications should be lower enough and not harm facilities. The upgraded biogas promoted in situ livestock biogas applications such as power generation or fuel for heat preservation.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Pig farm for this study

The selected commercial pig farm, the I-Yang Pig Farm raises about 1,500 pigs, and was in I-Lan County, Taiwan (available online: <https://www.facebook.com/iyangranch/>; accessed on 03 January 2022). The daily wastewater was about 48 m³/day. Analytical data of the wastewater samples showed that the suspended solids (SS), chemical oxygen demand (COD), and biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) of the raw wastewater after solid/liquid separation were 176 ± 76, 2262 ± 450, and 846 ± 279 mg/L, respectively. The biogas produced from the wastewater treatment facility of this pig farm was used for this study.

2.2. Farm-scale biogas bio-desulfurizing system (BBS)

The farm-scale biogas bio-desulfurizing system (BBS) was installed on the I-Yang Pig Farm. All processes of biogas desulfurization and upgrading are shown in Figure 1. The automatic operation design of BBS was modified from the design of a previous study (Su *et al.*, 2013). The modified BBS was constituted of a bio-filter (1 m outer diameter × 6 m height) filled with Raschig rings (i.e. hollow spherical polypropylene balls) (Sheng-Fa Plastics, Inc., Taiwan) and lightweight expanded clay aggregates (LECA). The condensed water from the bottom of the BBS was collected and analysed by ion chromatography (IC) as well as pH/conductivity check periodically. After the water quality of condensed water was stably acidic (e.g. pH < 2), the gas samples were collected from the inlet and outlet of BBS for gas chromatography (GC) analysis. H₂S in biogas was measured by a portable multi-gas detector or H₂S detector tubes for calculating the H₂S removal by the BBS.

Figure 1. Flowsheet of all processes for biogas production, desulphurization, and upgrading.

2.3. Dehydration and filtration reactor (DFR) and activated carbon reactor (ACR)

The DFR was constituted of a dehydration reactor and three filtration reactors (115 cm height \times 30 cm inner diameter, total volume = 81 L) (Figure 2). The dehydration reactor was packed with a mixture of Raschig rings and LECA. The ACR was the same container as DFR but filled with coconut shell-activated carbon pellets (diameter = 5 mm) and Raschig rings. The DFR and ACR were applied to remove excessive moisture and volatile organic compounds from the desulfurized biogas. The operation pressure was under ambient pressure.

Figure 2. Sketch and flowchart of the biogas bio-desulfurization system (BBS) in coordination with a biogas dehydration and filtration reactor (DFR) and hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption (HFCA) module.

2.4. Farm-scale hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption module (HFAM) for biogas upgrading

The farm-scale hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption module (HFAM) was installed followed by the farm-scale BBS in series. The HFAM (AuraMat-HFD CO₂-CH₄-15L-VC, Aura Material Inc., Hsinchu, Taiwan) (100 cm width \times 85 cm length \times 135 cm height, power voltage = 220 V 60/Hz) was constituted of two sets, Set #A and B, of hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption cartridges (60 cm length \times 3" outer diameter) (AuraMat-HTP-CO₂-A3, Aura Material Inc., Hsinchu, Taiwan) in parallel. The size of all biogas tubing, including biogas inlet, biogas purging, and biogas outlet tubing, was 1/2" tubing. Each adsorption cartridge set constitutes eight hollow fibre CO₂

adsorption cartridges in series. Two gas sampling ports were installed at the biogas inlet and outlet tubing for periodical biogas sampling. Desulfurized biogas was introduced into the module through two filtration cartridges, AuraMat-TP-HC-A-B and AuraMat-TP-HC-Oil-S (Aura Material Inc., Hsinchu, Taiwan) by an explosion-proof vacuum pump (flow rate = 15~26 L/min, No. N 026, KNF Neuberger, Inc., Trenton, NJ, USA) inside the module. The operation pressure of the CO₂ adsorption cartridge was < 1~2 kg/cm².

The sequencing of adsorption and regeneration processes for the HFAM was shown in Figures 3(a) and 3(b). Figure. 3(a) represents the adsorption process by Set A and the regeneration process by Set B simultaneously. Moreover, Figure. 3(b) represents the adsorption process by Set B and the regeneration process by Set A simultaneously. Therefore, the operation process of Set A was as follows in sequence: desulfurized biogas from the storage bags, filtration cartridge (AuraMat-TP-HC-A-B), hollow fibre adsorption cartridges (AuraMat-HTP-CO₂-A3), and then discharging upgraded biogas (Figure. 3(a), solid black line).

When hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption cartridges of Set A were saturated, the inlet biogas was automatically shifted to set B following the operation process for biogas upgrading (Figure. 3a, solid black line). Simultaneously, the hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption cartridges of Set A followed the regeneration process and were automatically regenerated. Therefore, the regeneration process of the HFAM was as follows in sequence: purged air, filtration cartridge (AuraMat-TP-HC-Oil-S), hollow fibre adsorption cartridges (AuraMat-HTP-CO₂-A3), vacuum pump, and then discharging gas (Figure. 3b, blue dashed line). Similarly, once the hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption cartridges of Set B are saturated, the operation process will automatically switch to the regeneration process (Figure. 3a, blue dashed line). Thus, Sets A and B were operated alternately.

2.5. Biogas upgrading using hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption module with automatic regeneration

The HFAM had to be warmed up for at least 2.5 h and then another 2.5 h for filling up biogas inside the cartridges of the CO₂ adsorption module before starting any time-course experiments. Desulfurized biogas was introduced into the biogas filtration cartridge (AuraMat-TP-HC-A-B, Aura Material Inc., Hsinchu, Taiwan) and then through eight independent hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption cartridges (AuraMat-HTP-CO₂-A3, Aura Material Inc., Hsinchu, Taiwan) of the Set A or B through an explosion-proof vacuum pump inside the adsorption module for time-course experiments of CO₂ removal from the biogas. Biogas samples were taken at 10 min intervals in an hour from the inlet and the outlet of the CO₂ adsorption cartridge module under the outlet biogas flow rates of 5, 10, 15, and 20 L/min. The hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption cartridges of Sets A and B have operated alternatively and regenerated automatically based on the signals on the control panel. Biogas samples were taken at 10 min intervals in an hour from the inlet and outlet of the adsorption cartridge module under various outlet biogas flow rates. The contents of all biogas samples were determined by using GC with a thermal conductivity detector (GC/TCD) (Su and Chung, 2021).

2.6. Analysis

2.6.1. Determination of pH, EC, and ions in liquid samples

Electrical conductivity (EC) and the pH of water samples were determined by a pH/conductivity meter (ExStik EC500, EXTECH Instrument, FLIR Commercial Systems, Goleta, CA, USA). Ion concentrations of water samples were determined by anion chromatography (IC) (Metrohm, 883 Basic IC Plus, Switzerland) equipped with an auto-sampler (863 Compact Autosampler). Anions were separated by Metrosep A Supp 5 (4 mm × 150 mm) column, and included SO₄²⁻, PO₄³⁻, NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻ and Cl⁻. Samples were diluted and filtered through a 0.2 mm filter before injecting them into ion chromatography.

Figure 3. Flow chart of the hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption system including operation process (in solid lines) and regeneration process (in dashed lines). Where Set A is under operation process (a) or Set B is under operation process (b).

2.6.2. H₂S determination in biogas samples

A portable multi-gas detector (ISC MX series, Industrial Scientific Co., PA, USA) was used to measure the concentration of H₂S on-site of the biogas samples from both inlet and outlet of the BBS. When the concentration of H₂S was over the detection limit of the portable multi-gas detector (sensor: H₂S: 0 – 697 mg/L, SO₂: 0 – 393 mg/L, O₂: 0 – 0.30 (% vol.), NH₃: 0 – 348 mg/L), a gas sampling pump (GV-100C gas sampling pump; Gastec Co., Japan) with H₂S detector tubes (H₂S = 14 – 5575 mg/L) (Gastec Co., Kanagawa, Japan) was applied for H₂S detection.

2.6.3. CH₄, CO₂ and N₂ determination in biogas samples

Tedlar® bags (SKC, PA, USA) with a single polypropylene fitting were used for collecting biogas samples from the inlets and outlets. The fitting contained a Teflon® syringe port-lined septum and a hose connection, which functioned as a shut-off valve for incoming and outgoing gas. Meanwhile, a 500 mL gas collector (GL Sciences Inc., Tokyo, Japan) was used to withdraw gas samples from the inlets and outlets of the PDRs. Biogas

samples were analysed for their composition by GC (Master GC, DANI Instruments, Marlborough, MA, USA), which was equipped with a TCD and Carboxen 1010 PLOT capillary column (30 m × 0.53 mm × 0.25 μm film thickness; Supelco Analytical of Sigma-Aldrich Co., PA, USA) (Su and Chung, 2021). Calibration curves of CH₄, CO₂, and nitrogen gas were obtained by the external standard method, and the calibration curve's correlation coefficient is > 0.995.

2.6.4. Estimation of carbon emission reduction

Estimation of carbon emission was carried out by applying clean development methodology and emission factors of stationary combustion (IPCC, 2006a). The baseline scenario and project scenario assumed coking coal or anthracite (100 tons/year) and upgraded biogas as the fuels for thermal power generation, respectively. The net caloric values (NCV) of biogas (refer to as slurry gas), anthracite, and coking coal as well as the global warming potential (GWP) of CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O were used for both baseline and project scenario carbon emission (Table 1). Moreover, the emission factors (EFs) of CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O for stationary combustion of biogas (as slurry gas), anthracite, and coking coal are used for calculation (Table 2). The carbon emission of the baseline scenario (t CO₂e/yr) is calculated based on EFs of coking coal or anthracite. Moreover, the carbon emission of the project scenario (t CO₂e/yr) is calculated by replacing coking coal or anthracite with biogas (slurry gas) and based on EFs of slurry gas as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Baseline scenario} &= 100 \text{ tons/yr} \times \text{NCV (coking coal or anthracite)} \times \text{EF (coking coal or anthracite)} \times \text{GWP}_{100} \\ \text{Project scenario} &= 100 \text{ tons/yr} \times \text{NCV (coking coal or anthracite)} \times \text{EF (slurry gas)} \times \text{GWP}_{100} \end{aligned}$$

Table 1. Net caloric value (NCV) for fuels and global warming potential (GWP) (IPCC, 2006b; IPCC, 2007).

Fuels		NCV (TJ/Gg)	
Gasoline		44.3	
Slurry gas		50.4	
Anthracite		26.7	
Coking coal		28.2	
Global Warming Potential (GWP ₁₀₀)			
GHGs	CO ₂	CH ₄	N ₂ O
CO ₂ e	1	25	298

Table 2. Default emission factors for stationary combustion of fuels (IPCC, 2006a).

Fuels	Emission Factors for Stationary Combustion (kg of greenhouse gas per TJ on an NCV basis)		
	kg-CO ₂ /TJ	kg-CH ₄ /TJ	kg-N ₂ O/TJ
Gasoline	69,300	3	0.6
Anthracite	98,300	1	1.5
Coking coal	94,600	1	1.5
Slurry gas	54,600	1*	0.1

2.6.5. Statistical analysis

Experimental data of water quality at different operation days and gas concentrations at different flow rate levels were analysed with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) by Origin 2020b software. When ANOVA identified a significant effect, Tukey's test was applied for multiple comparison tests. The student's T-test was applied to the data of the bio-desulfurization test and gas concentrations between the inlet and outlet of the CO₂ adsorption module. The significance level is 0.05.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The initiation of BBS and biogas desulfurization

The water quality indexes of dropping water, i.e., condensed liquid, from BBS at different operation days were significantly different over time except for nitrite and chloride (Table 3). The dropping water samples were from the oxidation of H₂S in biogas into the condensed liquid. Thus, the pH value of dropping water, $0.78 \pm 0.16 - 4.85 \pm 0.69$, decreased over operation time resulting from increased SO₄²⁻ concentrations ($p < 0.05$). Results showed that SO₄²⁻, PO₄³⁻, NO₃⁻, NO₂⁻, and Cl⁻ in dropping water over operation time were $1,873 \pm 197 - 14,462 \pm 1038$ mg/L ($p < 0.05$), $286 \pm 58 - 511 \pm 78$ mg/L ($p < 0.05$), $27 \pm 25 - 102 \pm 30$ mg/L ($p < 0.05$), $88 \pm 62 - 147 \pm 12$ mg/L, and $57 \pm 39 - 106 \pm 6$ mg/L ($p < 0.05$), respectively. The EC of dropping water over operation time was 5.56 ± 1.81 to over 400 mS/cm ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3). Thus, increased EC in the dropping water samples is closely related to the increase of both SO₄²⁻ and PO₄³⁻ concentrations.

Table 3. Continuous data of pH, electrical conductivity, and anions of the dropping water samples from a farm-scale BBS (n=20).

Operation time (days)	pH	E.C. (mS/cm)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg/L)	NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	NO ₂ ⁻ (mg/L)	Cl ⁻ (mg/L)
2	4.85 ± 0.69	5.56 ± 1.81	1873 ± 197	334 ± 57	102 ± 30	123 ± 86	68 ± 57
5	2.66 ± 0.15	7.76 ± 0.18	2819 ± 164	286 ± 58	62 ± 41	88 ± 62	106 ± 6
7	0.78 ± 0.16	> 400	14462 ± 1038	511 ± 78	27 ± 25	147 ± 12	57 ± 39
P-value	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	< 0.05	NS	NS

Mean \pm SD; NS: not significant.

The biogas samples from the inlet and outlet of BBS were collected and analysed after 60 operation days (Table 4). The un-desulfurized biogas contains 1967 ± 512 mg/L H₂S. After passing through BBS, the H₂S of biogas was removed by $96.7 \pm 6\%$. On the other hand, the desulfurized biogas only remained at 67 ± 121 mg/L H₂S (Table 4). In addition, the concentrations of N₂, CO₂, and CH₄ showed no significant difference between the biogas before and after desulfurization by BBS.

Table 4. The difference in biogas composition after bio-desulfurization (n=12).

	H ₂ S (mg/L)	Removal (%)	N ₂ (%)	CH ₄ (%)	CO ₂ (%)
Raw Biogas	1967 ± 512	-	14.9 ± 1.2	63.3 ± 1.9	21.9 ± 0.9
Bio-desulfurized Biogas	67 ± 121	96.7 ± 6	15.2 ± 1.2	63.7 ± 2.7	21.1 ± 1.6
P-value	< 0.05	-	NS	NS	NS

Mean \pm SD; NS: not significant.

The results showed that the pH value of dropping water from BBS decreased and its EC and SO₄²⁻ increased as the operation time went on. The H₂S removal from biogas by the BBS is followed by a series of oxidation-reduction reactions (H₂S \rightarrow S⁰ \rightarrow SO₄²⁻). According to a previous study, when dropping water had a pH < 2, the sulfur-oxidizing bacteria formed stable biofilms (Su et al., 2013). Thus, in this study, the dropping water from BBS became acid and contained high SO₄²⁻ indicating the system removed H₂S from biogas successfully. As expected, the further results of H₂S removal revealed that the BBS worked very well in removing H₂S from untreated biogas. This study demonstrated that the pH value of dropping water is a good indicator of BBS initiation.

3.2. The flow rate experiment of hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption for biogas upgrading

The gas composition of biogas samples from the inlet and outlet of the HFAM is presented in Table 5. Applied 5, 10, 15, and 20 L/min inlet flow rates to the module, the inlet CO₂ in desulfurized biogas was $34.3 \pm 2.6 - 34.7 \pm 1.5\%$ and the removal efficiency of CO₂ was 100%, i.e. the outlet CO₂ in upgraded biogas was $0.0 \pm 0.0\%$ (Table 5). However, the inlet CH₄ in desulfurized biogas was $60.0 \pm 0.3 - 61.2 \pm 1.3\%$ and the outlet CH₄ in upgraded biogas was $92.9 \pm 2.1 - 93.8 \pm 0.6\%$. As for N₂ content, the inlet desulfurized biogas was $4.5 \pm 1.3 - 5.5 \pm 0.3\%$ and the outlet upgraded biogas was $6.2 \pm 0.6 - 7.1 \pm 2.1\%$ (Table 5). The results implied that the HFAM module can only remove CO₂ efficiently and remained CH₄ and N₂ in the outlet biogas. Thus, changes

in CH₄ concentrations between the inlet and outlet biogas samples after the upgrading process at any inlet flow rates ($p < 0.05$).

Table 5. Carbon dioxide removal of the desulfurized biogas by hollow fibre (CO₂) adsorption module (n=12).

Inlet Bio-gas (L/min)	CH ₄ (%)				N ₂ (%)			CO ₂ (%)		
	Inlet	Outlet	Difference	P-value	Inlet	Outlet	Difference	Inlet	Outlet	Removal
5	60.0 ± 0.3	93.7 ± 1.1	+56.1	< 0.05	5.5 ± 0.3	6.3 ± 1.1	+13.9	34.5 ± 0.2	0.0 ± 0.0	100
10	60.8 ± 1.7	93.2 ± 0.7	+53.4	< 0.05	4.5 ± 0.8	6.8 ± 0.7	+50.0	34.7 ± 1.3	0.0 ± 0.0	100
15	61.2 ± 1.3	92.9 ± 2.1	+51.9	< 0.05	4.5 ± 1.3	7.1 ± 2.1	+59.0	34.3 ± 2.6	0.0 ± 0.0	100
20	60.3 ± 2.2	93.8 ± 0.6	+55.7	< 0.05	5.0 ± 0.7	6.2 ± 0.6	+24.2	34.7 ± 1.5	0.0 ± 0.0	100

Mean ± SD

The experimental results indicated that the HFAM was capable to remove CO₂ from the desulfurized biogas and promoting CH₄ concentrations within 5–20 L/min inlet flow rates. The CO₂ removal tendency of the HFAM for desulfurized biogas was the same as that of our previous pilot-scaled study (Su and Chung, 2021). The results showed that the methane purity of the previous study and this study was 86% and 93.6%, respectively (Su and Chung, 2021). Also, the CO₂ removal efficiency of the previous study and this study was 97.0% and 100%, respectively. This study with higher inlet biogas flow, i.e. higher biogas treatment volume, but consumed less electric energy (3.4 kWh/Nm³ CH₄) than our previous study (18.7 kWh/Nm³ CH₄) (Su and Chung, 2021) (Table 6). It implies that the higher the biogas treatment volume, the lower the operation cost of biogas upgrading. Moreover, a comparison of other hollow fibre membrane technique studies showed that the product CH₄ purity of this study was lower (93.6 %) than that of Žák et al. (2018). However, our study performed better CO₂ removal (100 %) and operated under ambient temperature and lower pressure with less energy consumption. The low CH₄ purity of the product might be owing to higher N₂ concentration in raw biogas. This limited the CH₄ purity in product gas after the upgrading process. Therefore, additional N₂ adsorption by a specific adsorption module should be considered for promoting higher CH₄ concentrations in upgraded biogas.

Table 6. The comparison of biogas upgrading indicators with the previous study.

	Scale	CH ₄ purity (% vol.)	CO ₂ removal (% vol.)	Operating conditions	Inlet biogas flow (L/min)	Energy consumption (kWh/Nm ³ CH ₄)
This work	Farm	93.6	100	2 bar, ambient temperature	20	3.4
Su and Chung (2021)	Pilot	86	97.0	Ambient pressure and temperature	1	18.7

3.3. Evaluation of upgraded biogas for power substitution

The revenue for electric power generation in different scenarios, 60%, 90%, and 95% methane in biogas, with either 30-kW or 65-kW generators, was shown in Table 7. Based on the 2023 feed-in tariff (FIT) for the biogas power generation from anaerobic digesters in Taiwan (0.24 USD/kWh) (TMOE, 2023) and the operation time of the power generator (350 d/yr), the revenue using a 30-kW generator was 30.2, 45.4, and 47.9 thousand USD/yr, respectively. On the other hand, the revenue using a 65-kW generator was 65.5, 98.3, and 103.7 thousand USD/yr, respectively (Table 7).

The fuel value of bio-neutral gas equal to liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) was calculated below: the maximum flow rate (20 L/min) was used to gain daily methane yields of 21.7 m³/d (Table 8). Then, the volume of LPG (20 kg/barrel) is 9,391 L per barrel, where the density of LPG (butane) is 0.575 kg/L at 15°C (Afrox, 2022) and 1 L-LPG can be expanded to produce 270 L-gas based on the data of Elgas limited (2021). The daily methane yields were converted into LPG barrel yields, which is 2.31 barrels/d. With further calculation, it is 843 barrels/yr (Table 8).

Table 7. Estimation of the revenue for power production under different methane concentrations in biogas with either a 30-kW or 65-kW generator.

Methane in biogas (%)	Generator capacity (kW)	Operation time (h/d)	*Daily Power Production (kWh/d)	Efficiency (%)	*Revenue for power generation (thousand USD/yr)
60	30	20	360	100	30.2
90			540	150	45.4
95			570	158	47.9
60	65	20	780	100	65.5
90			1,170	150	98.3
95			1,235	158	103.7

*Daily power production = methane in biogas × generator capacity × operation time

*Revenue for power generation = daily power production × operation time (350 d/yr) × feed-in tariff (0.24 USD/kWh in Taiwan in 2023)

Table 8. Estimation of the fuel values using upgrade biogas instead liquid petroleum gas (LPG).

Item	Value	Calculations	Item	Value	Calculations
Daily methane yields	21.7 m ³ /d	20 L/min × 60 min/h × 24 h/d × 80% productivity × 94% purity = 21.7 m ³ /d	The volume of liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) (20 kg/barrel)	9,391 L/barrel	20 kg/barrel ÷ 0.575 kg/L × 270 L-gas/L-LPG = 9391 L/barrel
Converting daily methane yields to LPG yields	2.31 barrels/d	21.7 m ³ /d ÷ 9.4 m ³ /barrel = 2.31 barrels/d	Converting yearly methane yields to LPG yields	843 barrels/yr	2.31 barrels/d × 365 d/yr = 843 barrels/yr

3.4. Estimation of installation and operation costs for biogas upgrading

The initial installation cost (78,284 USD) included re-generable (HFAM) (76,321 USD per set), dehydration and filtration reactor (DFR), and activated carbon reactor (ACR) (1,963 USD/set) (Table 9). Because several types of biogas desulfurization systems were adopted by different livestock farms with various installation costs, the installation cost of the farm-scale biogas bio-desulfurization system (BBS) was not included and calculated.

The annual operation cost (total cost = 4357 USD/yr) included the electricity cost of the HFAM, replacement of the adsorption, and filtration cartridges of HFAM (357 and 1,429 USD /yr, respectively). Thus, the daily operation cost not including installation cost is 12.1 USD/d. The upgraded biogas cost is 0.0004 USD/L (Table 9).

Table 9. Estimation of total costs for a farm-scale biogas upgrading system.

Installation cost		Operation cost	
Items	Price (USD)	Items	Price (USD/yr)
Installation of BBS	(35,714)	Electricity cost of HFAM	2,571
Installation of HFAM	76,321	Replacement of the packing materials (DFR and ACR)	357
Installation of DFR and ACR	1,963	Replacement of the adsorption and filtration cartridges (HFAM)	1,429
Total	78,284		4,357

A previous study using a pilot-scaled and integrated photocatalytic biogas desulfurizer and hollow fibre CO₂ adsorption module for the biogas flow rate of 1 L/min was successfully developed and tested (Su and Chung, 2021). The initial installation and operation cost of the pilot-scaled HFAM is 21,970 USD and 2,028 USD/yr, respectively (unpublished data). Moreover, at another on-planning full-scale centralized demonstration site for livestock biogas upgrading for the biogas flow rate up to 2000 L/min, the initial installation cost was about 183,333 USD (unpublished data provided by Aura Material Inc., Hsinchu, Taiwan). In other words, the higher the biogas flow rates for upgrading, the less the marginal installation and operation cost of the HFAM facility.

3.5. Estimation of carbon emission reduction

Assuming the use of coking coal or anthracite for the thermal power plant was 100 tons/yr and the calculations of carbon emission for stationary combustion were shown in Figure.4. The baseline carbon emissions of coking coal and anthracite are 268.1 and 263.7 t CO₂e/yr, respectively. When replaced with upgraded biogas, the project carbon emissions decreased to 154.1 and 145.9 t CO₂e/yr, respectively. In summary, the replacement of coking coal and anthracite by upgraded biogas for stationary combustion reduced 42.5% and 44.4% of carbon emissions, respectively. The local micro-grid system can be integrated by using upgraded biogas to replace coals and mitigate carbon dioxide emissions.

Figure 4. Comparison of the baseline scenario, project scenario, and emission reductions of carbon dioxide by replacing coking coal (CC) and anthracite (AN) with upgraded biogas for stationary combustion.

Overall, although applying a biogas desulfurization facility combined with the hollow fiber membrane technology is not an advanced idea, the combination of biogas bio-desulfurization and upgrading systems on a farm scale has never been reported.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The study successfully demonstrated the feasibility and effectiveness of a farm-scale biogas upgrading system combined with a bio-desulfurization system. Results showed that the biogas upgrading system provided the maximum daily treatment volume of 20 L/min and achieved 100% of CO₂ removal and 94% of methane content in the treated livestock biogas. The cost-effectiveness of the upgrading system showed that a larger-scale system is more beneficial. Finally, the replacement of anthracite and coking coal by upgraded biogas for stationary combustion significantly reduced above 40% of carbon dioxide emissions. National feed-in tariffs for developing renewable energy may be varied in different countries, but they can accelerate the growth of the domestic renewable energy industry. The achievement of this study can be applied to all decentralized pig farms worldwide for biogas upgrading and replacing coking coal or anthracite as sustainable cleaner energy by integrating local micro-grid systems.

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